

Chemical control of ufra disease in transplanted rice

M. L. Rahman and S. A. Miah, Plant Pathology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

We tested four nematicides, common salt, and zinc sulfate for control of ufra caused by the stem nematode

Ditylenchus angustus. Two-month-old BR4 plants with visible mottling and leaf chlorosis were collected from a farmer's field and planted 3 plants/pot in 3 replications for each treatment. Seven and 27 d after planting, 1.5 kg carbofuran 3%, 10.0 kg fenamiphos 5%, 10.0 kg disulfoton 10% 3.0 kg aldicarb 10% ai/ha, 67 kg common salt, and 20 kg zinc sulfate/ha were applied as basal, basal + foliar, or foliar. For foliar application, the chemicals were soaked 48 h in water, sieved through a fine cotton cloth, diluted to 120 ml to make an adequate amount to cover the leaf surface of the plants, and sprayed on the plants with a small hand sprayer. For

Effect of carbofuran 3% on ufra severity and yield of transplanted rice.^a Joydebpur, Bangladesh, 1984.

Carbofuran 3% (kg ai/ha)	Ufra severity (%)		Healthy panicles (%)	Yield (t/ha)
	Booting	Harvest		
0	81.2 a	69.7 a	30 c	05 b
0.5	73.7 a	49.4 a	51 b	1.0 b
1.0	49.6 ab	43.8 ab	56 ab	1.0 ab
1.5	28.3 b	31.3 b	69 a	1.6 a
F-values ^b	7.35*	4.78*	4.99*	8.10*
CV	23	21	17	31

^aAv of 4 replications. Column values with a common letter do not differ significantly at 0.05 level by DMRT. ^b* = significant at 0.05 level of significance.

basal + foliar treatment half the dose was used for each application. Control pots were sprayed with tap water.

At harvest, recovery was 64% with carbofuran, 69% with fenamiphos, and 73% with disulfoton. Plants treated with these nematicides yielded 14, 21, and 20 g/pot. There was no yield from other treatments. Secondary tillers of the three successful treatments were not ufra-infected. All tillers died in the other treatments.

We conducted a trial in an ufra-infested transplanted aman field to

identify the proper carbofuran dosage to be applied after plants show ufra symptoms. Carbofuran at 0.5, 1.0, or 1.5 kg ai/ha was incorporated in soil in 2-3 cm standing water at 1-mo intervals at tillering and late tillering. Carbofuran at 1.5 kg ai/ha gave best results (see table). In most cases, ufra infestation was less at harvest than at booting stage. The experiments showed that nematicides can control ufra in transplanted rice, even after symptoms have developed. ☞

Rice disease status in India

R. K. Upadhway, Directorate of Plant Protection, Quarantine, and Storage, N. H. IV, Faridabad, Haryana, India

Rice is planted on about 40.7 million ha in India. Yields often are substantially

reduced by disease. To monitor disease incidence, the Directorate of Plant Protection, Quarantine, and Storage and state departments of agriculture have organized insect pest and disease surveys since 1970. Twenty-six survey teams have covered standard routes through about 300,000 ha of rice land at 10-d intervals

since 1980. Disease severity has been rated using the 1980 Standard evaluation system for rice. The table shows major disease outbreaks and distribution.

Tungro virus is the most common disease. Most popular varieties are susceptible, including Tella Hamsa, Surekha, IET2508, IET1444, Co 40,

Present status and geographical distribution of major rice diseases in India.

State	Incidence of rice diseases ^a														
	B1	BS	NBLS	LSc	SR	ShB	ShR	Gld	FSm	KSm	Udb	BB	BLS	RTV	GSV
Andhra Pradesh	5-8 ^b	3-7 ^c	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	—	3-5 ^c	5-9 ^c	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	—	3-5 ^c	3-5 ^b	3-1 ^b	—
Assam	4-6 ^c	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	—	—	—	1-3 ^b	—	—	1-3 ^c	—	1-2 ^b	—
Bihar	3-5 ^b	3-7 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	3-5 ^c	3-5 ^b	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^c	1-3 ^c	—	0-1 ^b	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	3-7 ^b	—
Haryana	4-6 ^b	3-6 ^c	3-9 ^b	—	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^c	3-5 ^c	3-9 ^c	—	—	3-1 ^c	—	—	—
Karnataka	4-6 ^b	1-3 ^c	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^c	—	—	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^c	—	1-5 ^c	3-5 ^b	—	—	—
Kerala	—	1-3 ^b	—	1-3 ^b	—	3-5 ^c	—	—	—	—	1-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	—	1-2 ^b	—
Madhya Pradesh	5-7 ^b	3-6 ^c	0-1 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-7 ^c	1-3 ^c	5-9 ^c	5-7 ^d	1-3 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	—
Maharastra	3-5 ^b	3-6 ^c	—	1-3 ^b	—	1-3 ^b	—	—	1-3 ^c	—	1-5 ^c	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	—
Orissa	4-6 ^b	3-6 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	1-3 ^b	—	0-1 ^b	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	—				
Punjab	1-3 ^b	2-5 ^b	3-5 ^b	—	3-7 ^c	3-5 ^b	3-7 ^d	3-5 ^c	1-5 ^b	—	—	5-7 ^b	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	—
Tamil Nadu	3-5 ^b	2-4 ^b	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	—	1-5 ^b	3-7 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-7 ^c	0-1 ^b
Uttar Pradesh	2-6 ^b	3-1 ^c	—	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^b	1-3	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^b	—	—	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-7 ^b	—
West Bengal	1-3 ^b	1-3 ^b	—	1-3 ^b	3-5 ^b	1-3	3-5 ^c	1-3 ^b	—	—	—	3-5 ^b	1-3 ^b	3-7 ^c	—

^a B1 = blast, BS = brown spot, NBLS = narrow brown leaf spot, LSc = leaf scald, SR = stem rot, ShB = sheath blight, ShR = sheath rot, Gld = glume discoloration, FSm = false smut, KSm = kernel smut, Udb = udbatta disease, BB = bacterial blight, BLS = bacterial leaf streak, RTV = rice tungro virus, GSV = grassy stunt virus. ^b Isolated/rare fields. ^c Scattered/sporadic. ^d Widespread.